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Localized Video Clips and the Academic Performance of Selected Grade 3 Pupils in Araling Panlipunan at Peñafrancia Elementary School

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the effectiveness of localized video clips in the performance of selected pupils in Peñafrancia Elementary School for School Year 2021 – 2022. The respondents of the study were the 40 selected grade three pupils of Peñafrancia Elementary School. Descriptive survey research design was utilized.

The study concluded that different localized resources help pupils learn the subject more effectively. Pupils have higher favorable attitudes toward the Araling Panlipunan subject. For pupils in grade three level, it makes Araling Panlipunan instruction more engaging, applicable, realistic, and appealing. The localized video clips in Araling Panlipunan allows pupils the chance to widen and deepen their knowledge by providing a variety of first-hand, developmentally appropriate experiences and by supporting them in obtaining knowledge by portraying their experiences. Furthermore, the localized video clips in Araling Panlipunan could help pupils learn and perform the necessary competencies, particularly in their abilities. The developed resources give pupils the fundamental knowledge they need to understand and apply different ideas

Context and Rationale

The pandemic has brought many changes in every part of the world especially with the education sector. It had introduced a different kind of teaching-learning delivery where both teacher and pupils are far from each other, but the student is still learning. It paved way to different ideas from teachers to help their pupils continue to learn even if there is the long distance between them.

The greatest pandemic in over 100 years has raised many questions about its direct and indirect effects on children and young people. One of the most prominent sets of concerns has focused on learning losses. These concerns have emerged because most of the world's children have missed at least a few weeks of regular schooling, some young people have missed an entire year or more, remote learning alternatives have often proved problematic with access to them being unequal, on-site learning with physical distancing has sometimes diminished or disrupted the regular learning experience, and millions of young

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people fell off the educational radar altogether, perhaps never to return, when their schools shut down (Vegas, 2021).

For educators, the COVID-19 Pandemic is a quintessential adaptive and transformative challenge, one for which there is no preconfigured playbook that can guide appropriate responses. Education leaders must swiftly design responses – and with specific contexts in mind – as the pandemic runs its course (Reimer et. al., 2020).

DepEd Order No. 12 s. 2020 stands on the principle to ensure learning continuity through K-12 curriculum adjustments, alignment of learning materials and deployment of multiple learning delivery modalities.

Peñafrancia Elementary School offered two distance learning modalities: online and modular. The teacher as a researcher observed the challenge faced those enrolled under modular learning. During distribution and retrieval, there are concerns raised by parents that their children have a hard time trying to understand their lesson in Araling Panlipunan that the teacher is not around. Hence, this prompts the researcher to come up with an idea that may help her pupils better learn their lessons even if she cannot teach them face to face and test its effectiveness on their academic performance. Thus, the conduct of this study.

Innovation, Intervention and Strategy

The researcher developed a localized instructional video on the lessons in Araling Panlipunan. This video contained seven lessons of the third grading period. Every week, the researcher will send the video lessons via Messenger to the selected respondents and watched them as their guide in answering the activities in their module.

Research Questions

This study determined the effectiveness of the localized video clips on the academic performance of selected grade 3 pupils in Araling Panlipunan at Peñafrancia Elementary School.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of performance of the pupils based on their pre-test and post-test scores before and after exposure to localized video clips in Araling Panlipunan?
2. Is there a significant difference between the level of performance of the pupils based on their pre-test and post-test scores before and after exposure to localized video clips in Araling Panlipunan?
3. What action plan may be proposed to improve the localized video clips in Araling Panlipunan?

Action Research Methods

a. Participants and/other Sources of Data and Information

Participants of the study will be 40 selected grade 3 pupils studying in Peñafrancia Elementary School. These participants were chosen using convenience sampling. These participants are pupils of the researcher and because of their ease of access, readiness to be a part of the study and is available at any given time slot convenient to the researcher and them, therefore, they were selected.

b. Data Gathering Methods

To gather the data needed, the researcher prepared a same set of questions for the pre-test and post-test of lessons discussed in the video clips. She also prepared the localized video clips that she used in the class. After making such preparations, the pre-test was then administered. Answer sheets were collected and computed. Next was sending the localized

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video clips through the parents' group chat. A post-test was conducted after the pupils were exposed to localized video clips. Answer sheets for the post-test were collected and computed also.

c. Data Analysis Plan

Statistical tools and descriptive analysis were used in analyzing the collected data. Mean Scores and Mean Percentage Scores were used to determine the based on their pre-test and post-test scores before and after exposure to localized video clips in Araling Panlipunan. Dependent t-test was also employed to determine the significant difference between the level of performance of the pupils based on their pre-test and post-test scores before and after exposure to localized video clips in Araling Panlipunan. Furthermore, descriptive analysis was used to identify the action plan to improve the localized video clips in Araling Panlipunan.

Discussion of Results and Reflection

Level of Performance of the Pupils Based on their Pretest and Posttest Scores Before and After Exposure to Localized Video Clips

Table 1 presents the mean and mean percentage score on the level of performance of the pupils based on their pre-test and post-test scores before and after exposure to localized video clips in Araling Panlipunan.

Table 1

Level of Performance of the Pupils Based on their Pre-test and Post-test Scores

Score	Verbal Interpretation	Pre-test			Post-test		
		f	%	R	f	%	R
20	Outstanding	-	-	-	7	17.5	5
16 - 20	Very Satisfactory	-	-	-	21	52.5	4
11 – 15	Satisfactory	9	22.5	2	12	30.0	1
6 – 10	Fairly Satisfactory	29	72.5	1	-	-	-
5 and below	Did not meet expectations	2	5.0	3	-	-	-
Total		40	100.0		40	100.0	
Highest Score		11			20		
Lowest Score		4			12		
Mean		9.45			17.07		
Mean Percentage Score		47.25			85.37		

As portrayed from the table, with regard to the level of performance of the grade three pupils in Araling Panlipunan in the pre-test, they obtained a mean score of 9.45 with verbal interpretation of Fairly Satisfactory. Likewise, after being exposed to localized video in Araling Panlipunan obtained a mean score of 17.07 which is higher than the pre-test mean score which is interpreted Very Satisfactory. With the mean percentage score of 47.25 and 85.37, it

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could be observed that the grade three pupils have different performance before and after exposure to localized video clips in Araling Panlipunan.

This means that the grade three pupils improved their performance after being exposed to localized video clips in Araling Panlipunan. After being exposed to the localized video clips in Araling Panlipunan, the pupils' abilities have also improved to the level required for grade three pupils. It also demonstrates how pupils' performance improve as a result of engaging in newly localized learning materials.

The results imply that different localized resources help pupils learn the subject more effectively. Pupils have higher favorable attitudes toward the Araling Panlipunan subject. For pupils in grade three level, it makes Araling Panlipunan instruction more engaging, applicable, realistic, and appealing. The localized video clips in Araling Panlipunan allows pupils the chance to widen and deepen their knowledge by providing a variety of first-hand, developmentally appropriate experiences and by supporting them in obtaining knowledge by portraying their experiences.

Significant Difference between the Level of Performance of the Pupils Based on Their Pretest and Posttest Scores Before and After Exposure to Localized Video Clips

Table 2 presents significant difference on the level of performance of the pupils based on their pretest and posttest scores before and after exposure to localized video clips.

Table 2
Significant Difference between the Level of Performance of the Pupils Based on Their Pre-test and Post-test Scores Before and After Exposure to Localized Video Clips

Aspect	Mean	t-value	p-value	Ho	Verbal Interpretation
Pretest	9.45	2.022	0.000	Rejected	Significant
Posttest	17.07				

As shown in the table, there is a significant difference on the level of performance of the pupils before and after exposure to localized video clips as revealed in the pre-test and post-test results for, they obtained the computed p-value of .000, which is less than the .05 probability value. This rejects the null hypothesis.

Findings indicate that the null hypothesis is rejected stating that there is no significant difference on the level of performance of the pupils before and after exposure to localized video clips as revealed in the pre-test and post-test results.

Findings imply a marked difference on the performance of the pupils exposed to localized video clips in Araling Panlipunan as revealed in their pre-test and post-test results. Furthermore, the localized video clips in Araling Panlipunan could help pupils learn and perform the necessary competencies, particularly in their abilities. The developed resources give pupils the fundamental knowledge they need to understand and apply different ideas.

Proposed Action Plan to Improve the Localized Video Clips in Araling Panlipunan

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The table presents the proposed action plan to improve the use of localized video clips in Araling Panlipunan.

Proposed Action Plan in Order to Improve the Localized Video Clips in Araling Panlipunan

Objectives	Strategy	Time Frame	Persons Involved	Expected Output
Provide Instructional Module on how to use the Localized Instructional Video in Araling Panlipunan	Create a step-by-step instructional module on how to use the localized instructional video in Araling Panlipunan with its use on lesson planning.	September to December	Araling Panlipunan Teacher	100% of the Araling Panlipunan teachers were provided with Instructional Module on how to use the Localized Instructional Video in Araling Panlipunan
Incorporate differentiated teaching strategies suited for all type of learners in the localized instructional video	Research on differentiated teaching strategies suited for all type of learners in the video	September to June	Grade 3 Pupils, Researcher	100% of the Grade 3 pupils' needs were catered through differentiated teaching strategies used in the localized instructional video.
Innovate more localized instructional videos in Araling Panlipunan	Create more localized instructional videos in Araling Panlipunan using other topics.	September to June	Araling Panlipunan Teacher	100% of the topics in Araling Panlipunan were created with localized instructional videos.

Plans for Dissemination and Utilization

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The result of this study will be disseminated in LAC Sessions wherein other teachers will be informed of the developed materials and how to use it as a teaching strategy in the classroom discussion. Also, the preparation of materials will be shown to other teachers for them to have a guide in preparing the same thing to be used in the room. This research study will also be open for publication and presentation in research conference.

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The Researcher Made Videoclips
Araling Panlipunan 3
Quarter 3

Week 1- MELCs -Nailalarawan ang kultura ng mga lalawigan sa kinabibilangang rehiyon

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AP3PKR- IIIa-1

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Week 2 MELCs-

Naipaliliwanag ang kaugnayan ng heograpiya sa pagbuo at paghubog ng uri ng pamumuhay ng mga lalawigan at rehiyon. **AP3PKR- IIIa-2**

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Week 3 MELCs-Nailalarawan ang pagkakakilanlang kultural ng kinabibilangang rehiyon
AP3PKR- IIIb-c-3

Natutukoy ang mga wika at diyalekto ng ating lalawigan at rehiyon.

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Natutukoy ang mga katawagan sa ibat ibang layon.

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ang mga saksi nito sa pagkakakilanlang kultura ng sariling lalawigan at rehiyon
AP3PKR- IILD-4

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Week 5-6 MELCs-Naihahambing ang pagkakatulad at pagkakaiba ng mga kaugalian, paniniwala at tradisyon sa sariling lalawigan sa karatig lalawigan sa kinabibilangang rehiyon at sa ibang lalawigan at rehiyon

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Natutukoy ang mga pangkat ng tao sa ating Rehiyon

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Week 7-8 MELCs Napahahalagahan ang iba't ibang pangkat ng tao sa lalawigan at Rehiyon
AP3PKR- IIIIF-7

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